

A graph-based socio-economic analysis of Steemit

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Abstract—Online Social Networks (OSNs) have changed the way of how people interact, however lately people are questioning more and more their business models. During the last ten years, new solutions based on decentralised architectures have been proposed, namely, Decentralized Online Social Networks (DOSNs) and Blockchain Online Social Medias (BOSMs). DOSNs were introduced several years ago and their main goal is the preservation of the privacy of the users in such a way that the data and the content of a user are always under their control. BOSMs leverage the usage of blockchain either to enforce the privacy of the users or to redistribute the wealth generated by the platform through a rewarding system. Steemit is the most stable and well-known BOSM with more than 1 million registered users, where users can create their own Social Network by following other users. At the best of our knowledge, no study exists on the relation between the economic and social characteristics of BOSMs and on the way the rewarding system affects the social activity.

The main goal of this paper is to evaluate the characteristics of the Steemit follower-following graph to understand how the social and the economic aspects of BOSMs intertwine and influence each other. We study the properties of the Steemit follower-following graph and a few selected hotspot contents. The analysis shows that users are highly encouraged to be socially active, especially producing content, but the richest users are not also the most social ones, which suggests us that users can get rich without much involvement in the platform, using external mechanisms.

Index Terms—Social Networks, Blockchain, Steemit, Graph Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Online Social Networks (OSNs) are one of the most popular web applications, and users entrust their data to them and share personal content through them. The business model of these platforms is based on giving the users services free of charge to make it desirable, but, in return, everything users share on the platform becomes property of the platform owner and can be used at will. The activity of the users is then used by the platform owners in order to generate a revenue which economically sustains the platform. Many questions are arising concerning how the data of the users is handled, if their privacy is respected, and whether the business model is fair or not. During the last years, two new business models were introduced focusing either on increasing the privacy of the users or in redistributing the revenue of the platform among the users. Accordingly, new platforms were born to implement these business models. To remedy the privacy deficiencies [1] and the scandals related to its disclosure, such as Cambridge

Analytica¹, Decentralized Online Social Networks (DOSNs) have been introduced. A DOSN is an online social network implemented on a distributed platform, so that there is no central provider, but usually a set of peers that cooperate to run the system. In these platforms users have complete control over their data and can decide the trusted entities they are willing to share their data with.

Recently, thanks to the diffusion of the blockchain technology, its application in the field has gathered momentum. The idea behind Blockchain Online Social Media (BOSM) is to employ the blockchain technology for different purposes, such as to decentralize the control on social data, in some cases to let users maintain control of their social content [2] or for introducing a rewarding system. In particular, the current trend is to reward content creators for the valuable content, following principles coming from the attention economy [3]. The business model of paying users for the quality content they create is very appealing. Indeed, current BOSMs let the data to be visible to anyone and encourage users to produce good-quality content by rewarding the ones that are evaluated positively by the community in order to limit the spread of fake news. Rewards are usually awarded as cryptocurrency, not fiat currency, thus introducing an economic side of the service, intertwined with the social one.

During the last five years, several BOSMs have been presented, such as Sapien², Peepeth³, Minds⁴, Appics⁵, Hive Blog⁶, and Steemit⁷, which is currently the most successful proposal with more than 1 million registered users. Even if the basic motivations of these platforms are clear [4], we still lack knowledge about the real socio-economic behaviour of the BOSM users. Indeed, the main properties of current OSNs have been studied in depth in terms of graph properties [5], [6], [7], [8], communities [9], [10], influential nodes [11], [12], bot detection [13], etc., instead a deep analysis of BOSMs, highlighting, in particular, how social interactions are affected by the rewarding system in order to understand if they can be considered the next generation of Social Media, has not yet been performed. This economic side of BOSMs can affect and completely change the social aspect of a Social Media as we know.

For these reasons, in this paper we investigate how the social and the economic aspect of BOSMs intertwine and influence each other by taking Steemit as case study, because it is considered both the most well-known and the most widely-

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¹<https://www.theguardian.com/news/series/cambridge-analytica-files>

²<https://www.sapien.network/>

³<https://peepeth.com/welcome>

⁴<https://www.minds.com>

⁵<https://appics.com/index.html>

⁶<https://hive.blog/>

⁷<https://steemit.com>

used BOSM. Indeed Steemit is the first proposal that inspired several other BOSMs and influenced many of their aspects, including the rewarding systems. To reach our goal, we collect data from the Steem blockchain, which is the social blockchain containing the social data shared in Steemit by using the official API, and we build the follower-following graph [14]. We can summarize the contributions of the paper as follows:

- a description of the main features of Steemit, with a particular emphasis on the rewarding system and on the users that populate the platform;
- a detailed description of the multi-currency system adopted by Steemit and its connections with other currencies, pointing out strengths and weaknesses of this system;
- the construction of the follower-following graph, obtained by parsing the Steem blockchain, and the study of its structural and topological properties;
- the study of the impact of an economic layer in the platform from a graph theory perspective and from the analysis of a selected hotspot contents;
- the comparison of the platform with respect to other popular analogous social services such as Facebook [5], Twitter [14], [15], and others [6], [7], to further increase our knowledge of the platform and to identify analogies with other social networks.

The Steemit follower-following graph consists of 1.2 million users and 98 million directed "follows" relationships. The most important result emerging from our analyses is that richest users are not the ones most engaged in social activities, both in terms of social relationships and in terms of number of posts produced. We identify that this is due to the possibility of the users to buy cryptocurrency using external exchangers. While at a first glance this may seem harmless, wealthy users can be very influential on the platform, which leads to the contradiction that the most influential users bought their power using external mechanisms. Finally, the comparison with other popular social networking services uncovers that the Steemit follower-following graph shows properties which are similar to the early stages of Facebook [5].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the background. Section 3 presents the main features of the platform which are needed to understand the experimental evaluation. Section 4 presents how we gather the dataset, extract the graph, and finally the results. Section 5 draws conclusions and points out possible future works.

II. BACKGROUND

DOSNs [16] are Online Social Networks implemented by exploiting decentralized networks, such as P2P networks, that provide the decentralization of social services. During the last ten years several DOSNs have been proposed [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], but mainly these are academic proposals. Among the public available systems, Fediverse⁸, a confederation of federated platforms able to communicate thanks to the communication protocols used in Fediverse, can

be considered the most important project. The first big project included in Fediverse is Diaspora [24], founded in 2010. Diaspora is based on three key principles: decentralization, freedom, and privacy. The platform allows users to set up their own server (called "pod") to host content. Pods can then interact to share status updates, and other social data by exploiting specific protocols.

Another important platform is Mastodon, a popular federated alternative to Twitter, with more than 2 million users. Mastodon⁹ represents today the most important system of the Fediverse project. It is a microblog platform where users can follow others users, even if they are hosted on the same instance.

Other two important platforms included in Fediverse are Friendica and PixelFed.

Friendica¹⁰ has an emphasis on extensive privacy settings. Friendica users can connect with others via their own Friendica server, but may also fully integrate contacts from other platform, such as Twitter, Diaspora, Pump.io, etc. It provides private conversation groups and one-to-one private messaging on supported protocols.

PixelFed¹¹ represents an interesting alternative to Instagram and other photo sharing platforms. It is a free and ethical photo sharing platform, powered by ActivityPub federation. PixelFed is an open-source, federated platform. As the previous platforms, PixelFed uses federated servers where data are stored, and specific protocols to allow users to communicate across all servers.

DOSNs represent the first evolution of centralized OSNs. However, thanks to the introduction of the blockchain technology, BOSMs have been proposed as another class of distributed social solutions. We recall that a blockchain, which is one of the instances of the more general distributed ledger technology, is a chain of blocks that contains transactions between users of the P2P network that manages it. The blockchain presents key characteristics of decentralization, persistency, anonymity, tamper freeness and auditability [25]. Indeed, during the last ten years, the blockchain technology has been applied to several fields, and BOSMs [4] are currently an interesting application field. The main goal of these applications is to overcome the issues concerning fake news and censorship, by exploiting the blockchain in particular for the implementation of a rewarding strategy.

Several BOSMs have been already developed. The most famous is Steemit, which has reached more than 1 million users in the last years, and it represents today an important alternative to centralized OSNs. The description of the relevant system features is detailed in Section III.

Peepeth is a Twitter-like application which runs over Ethereum, and it is based on Peepeth, an open-source smart contract running on the Ethereum blockchain (data storage), and Peepeth.com, the front-end of the smart contract. Data is openly stored on the Ethereum blockchain, so that anyone can monitor Peepeth's public data.

⁹<https://joinmastodon.org/>

¹⁰<https://friendi.ca/>

¹¹<https://pixelfed.org/>

⁸<https://fediverse.party/>

Sapien¹² provides a platform to publish, access, and view social content. It uses a rewarding system to reward content creators and those who consume and curate it. It is built on the Ethereum blockchain, and uses an ERC-20 utility token, the SPN. Content can be public or private, which means that the platform guarantees a level of visibility of social data.

Minds¹³ is an open-source BOSM, where users earn crypto tokens for their contributions to the network. The tokens can be used for several purposes. Indeed, they can be exchanged for more views on content or sent to other channels as a tip or paid subscription.

Hive Blog is one of the many websites that are powered by the Hive blockchain, a new blockchain that originated as a fork of Steem. It is a new platform which, at the moment, presents the same characteristics of Steemit.

Appics is a reward-based social media application that runs on top of the Steem blockchain¹⁴, enabling people to connect and allowing all participants to benefit. It is the very first Smart Media Token based on the Steem blockchain and was created in full cooperation with Steemit.

An exhaustive overview of the main motivation of BOSMs and several technological details are proposed in [4]. In terms of academic proposals, BCSON [26] represents a BOSM focused on privacy issues, when the blockchain is used as a trusted server to provide central control services.

At the best of our knowledge, BOSMs have not yet been studied in depth, in particular to evaluate their social and economic properties.

A. Summary and Comparison

Table I summarizes the main characteristics of the proposed DOSNs and BOSMs platforms. We provide a set of properties in order to highlight the main differences concerning social and technical aspects between the two types of technologies. First, we provide the type of the platform: incentivized Social Media (BOSM) or Decentralized Online Social Networks (DOSN). Then, we classify a set of existing proposals with respect to the year of the official release, the type of consensus protocol, the underlying blockchain, the social network model (symmetric/asymmetric), privacy, data storage, and the level of decentralization. This level is categorized as Fully Decentralized (FD), Federated (F), and Partially Decentralized (PD).

The main difference between DOSNs and BOSMs, as shown in Table I is the usage of the blockchain technology. Most current public DOSNs are federated, and the most important ones are included in the Fediverse project. Federation permits to apply the decentralization at the server level. Users can have their own servers, and servers can communicate in a decentralized way. Instead, BOSMs are platforms partially decentralized, which means that data are stored in servers or distributed file systems, such as IPFS. It is worth to notice that no current public DOSN proposals are fully decentralized, even if several proposed DOSNs [22], [17], [23], mainly academic ones, present a complete level of decentralization.

Fig. 1: Number of active users in the most popular BOSMs.

All the proposed systems refer to blogs or content sharing platforms, and they have a structure similar to Facebook, Twitter, Reddit, and Instagram. Concerning the privacy issue, DOSNs propose specific solutions for privacy, as described in [27], instead BOSMs exploit the blockchain, which is a public ledger, and so everyone can see everything. Social content can be stored unencrypted in the blockchain, as in Steemit, or can be stored in external storages, and so not publicly visible, as for Sapien and Peepeth. The external storage is used because it is expensive to store all data in a blockchain that requires fee, such as Ethereum. As concerns the anonymity of users, Steemit uses pseudonyms, and it does not provide anonymity. The other presented BOSMs do not provide a publicly available content. For example, Minds provides an encrypted messenger which ensures privacy. Indeed, Minds has zero-knowledge of the contents of user conversations. Furthermore, anonymity option grants users the ability not to reveal their identity. The platforms described in Table I are the main used ones among the public available DOSNs platforms, and they face the privacy issue with the federated approach. Indeed, users are allowed to run their own servers or choose available servers provided by other users. Data are stored in these private servers which communicate between them with encrypted communications. By comparing the number of active users of these platforms, in order to highlight the most active ones, as shown in Figure 1, we can say that Mastodon represents the most used DOSN with more than 1 million of active users, instead Steemit is the most used BOSM, with more than 550,000 active users. Considering that the aim of this work is to analyse the socio-economic aspects in BOSMs, we decide to analyse Steemit because it represents an important case study comparing it with the other BOSMs.

III. THE STEEMIT ECOSYSTEM

Steemit is a Medium¹⁵-like platform where people can produce, comment, evaluate, and share content. The content produced is evaluated by the users of the platform through two kinds of votes: upvote for a positive evaluation, and downvote for a negative evaluation. A special feature of Steemit is that

¹²<https://www.sapien.network/>

¹³<https://www.minds.com/>

¹⁴<https://steem.com/>

¹⁵<https://medium.com/>

TABLE I: Most popular DOSNs and BOSMs.

Platform	Year	Type	Consensus	Blockchain	Privacy	Data Storage	Dec. Level	SM Type
<i>Diaspora</i>	2010	DOSN	-	-	Individual privacy settings and encryption	Servers (pods)	F	Macroblogging
<i>Friendedica</i>	2010	DOSN	-	-	Individual privacy settings, access lists, and encryption	Servers (nodes)	F	Macroblogging
<i>Minds</i>	2015	BOSM	PoW	Ethereum	Encrypted messenger and Anonymity option	Cassandra & Elasticsearch	PD	Content Sharing
<i>Steemit</i>	2016	BOSM	DPoS	Steem	Data are publicly available. No anonymity	Blockchain & IPFS	PD	Content Sharing
<i>Sapien</i>	2016	BOSM	PoW	Ethereum	Anonymous transactions.	Blockchain & IPFS	PD	Content Sharing
<i>Mastodon</i>	2016	DOSN	-	-	Per-content privacy setting	Servers (instances)	F	Microblogging
<i>Peepeth</i>	2018	BOSM	PoW	Ethereum	Anonymous transactions.	Blockchain & IPFS	PD	Content Sharing
<i>Appics</i>	2018	BOSM	DPoS	Steem	Data are publicly available. No anonymity	Blockchain & IPFS	PD	Content Sharing
<i>PixelFed</i>	2018	DOSN	-	-	Data are stored in private servers	Servers	F	Image sharing
<i>Hive Blog</i>	2020	BOSM	DPoS	Hive	Data are publicly available. No anonymity	Blockchain & IPFS	PD	Content Sharing

Fig. 2: The currencies used by Steemit and how to convert from one to the others. Between parentheses the time required to complete the conversion.

the author of the content gets an economic reward if the published content is evaluated as high quality and positively engages other users. Steemit is born as the killer application of Steem¹⁶, a public and open blockchain, which differs from other blockchains, like Bitcoin and Ethereum, because it has been designed to natively support social applications[28].

Further differences are:

- Steem is based on a multi-token economy, indeed multiple cryptocurrencies i.e. STEEM, VEST, and STEEM Blockchain Dollars (SBD), coexist in the Steem ecosystem.
- In contrast to other common blockchains, Steem supports a rich set of transactions, each of which has a specific meaning, mainly *social* or *economic*.

Steemit stores the activity of its users on the blockchain in the form of (unencrypted) transactions on the Steem blockchain. Therefore, not only money transfers, but also social actions, such as writing a content, upvoting a content, following another user, and so on, take the form of a transaction in the blockchain. This is a crucial feature of the platform which makes it censorship resistant. Larger contents, such as videos or pictures, are stored with the support of the Inter Planetary File System (IPFS).

The idea to reward users for valuable content derives both from the token and from the attention economy [3]. The result is that each user is encouraged to actively participate to the growth of the community and the more he/she contributes, the more he/she is rewarded through cryptocurrency payments and gets visibility and influence [29]. Given its primary importance in the platform, we present the relevant features of the economic system of the platform. A first description of the three currencies is presented in [30]. In this paper, we propose a more detailed, up-to-date, and technical description of the multi-currency system adopted. As we mentioned beforehand, in Steem there are three currencies which coexists: STEEM, VEST, and SBD. STEEM is the liquid currency of the platform, that is normally exchanged between users, and can either be stored for future payments, or be used to make a long term investment on the platform. These long term investments consist in turning (part of) the STEEMs one holds in VESTs, through an operation called "power-up". The amount of VESTs one holds show how much commitment or investment he/she has on the platform. VESTs cannot be traded among users, and moreover they can be traded back to STEEMs, but this conversion, called "power-down" requires a total of 13 weeks to complete, independently on how much VESTs is being powered down, and each week a portion (1/13th) of the requested VESTs is converted back to STEEMs. Per se, owning VESTs over STEEMs is a disadvantage, therefore the developers added two key features. Firstly, the whole economic system is inflationary, meaning that the amount of STEEM needed to acquire a VEST (STEEM to VEST exchange rate) is going to increase over time. Secondly, the more VESTs a user holds the more influence it has over the distribution of the reward funds through upvotes and downvotes, which is a key feature of the platform. These two mechanisms should incentivize Steemit users not to hold too many liquid STEEMs in their account, but rather to convert most of them to VESTs and keep them in that form. Finally, to introduce some market stability, and to make the whole economy also accessible for people outside the platform, a third currency was introduced: the SBD. It is, economically, more stable because the exchange rate is always

¹⁶<https://steem.com/>

kept close to 1 USD, and to deny possible speculations with it, the conversion from SBD to STEEM is executed 3.5 days after its request, while converting from STEEM to SBD is possible only through the internal market. STEEMs and SBDs can be bought from exchangers, however, since SBDs are created to maintain always a constant exchange rate with the USD, they are not necessarily always available, while the only way to obtain VESTs is through the power-up operation. In Figure 2 we show a recap of the three currencies present in the Steemit ecosystem and the time required to make a conversion. At first glance, this three-currency system has a solid design, where each currency has a specific purpose: STEEM for everyday economic transaction, VEST cannot be traded but give more power on the platform, and SBD is a stablecoin to let people easily enter the currency ecosystem. However, we point out two major drawbacks of this system. Firstly, STEEM, and in some way also SBD, is a very volatile currency, and its value can float quite rapidly, which makes it extremely desirable for people who want to speculate on these systems. Secondly, through the usage of external exchangers, it is very easy for everyone to acquire a considerable amount of STEEM, and then power-up to acquire VESTs. In this way, one can cheat the whole rewarding system and can acquire a lot of influence and power on the platform without ever contributing to it. Indeed, this mechanism is extremely controversial because it lets rich people take over the platform and have a strong influence on the contents rewards.

A. Users' Roles and Reward

Steemit allows anyone to become a user, and being a user is not mandatory to read the contents. Users in Steemit can have different social roles provided by the network:

- **Witness.** It is a particular user who operates a witness server and has some additional tasks, such as the creation of new blocks of the blockchain and the periodical publication of a *price feed*. Each witness can be voted by other users and they are ranked based on the received votes¹⁷. They are generally the most reliable and influential users of the network and they are the ones who approve hard forks, indeed it happens only if 67% of the top witnesses agree¹⁸.
- **Creator.** A user is defined a creator when he/she publishes a new content and he/she is rewarded for its value.
- **Curator.** A user is defined a curator when he/she contributes by adding value to the contents produced by other users; this operation takes place through upvoting the contents.

Whenever a content is created, it can be modified only up to 7 days after its creation. After this time span, the content is finalized, it cannot be edited anymore, and the rewards for the creator and the curators are effectively computed and awarded. Users have two options how to get the rewards: Power up 100%, or 50%/50%. In the first case, all the STEEM value of the reward is powered up and granted to the user as VEST. In

Fig. 3: User levels in Steemit, and the amount of VEST required to reach a rank. It is important to notice that the amount of VEST required to increase the level is ten times higher than the previous one.

the latter case, which is the default one, half of the reward is powered up while the other half is granted as liquid currency (a combination of STEEMs and SBDs). Users can also decide to decline the payout for a specific content they created and receive no rewards for being creators of that content. The reward for a content is distributed between the participants: 50% of the rewards goes to the author, and 50% is granted to the curators. The total payout of a content is based on the VESTs of the curators and by how much *voting power* they decide to give to their vote, but the reward granted to each curator is based also on the voting position: being the first curator pays better. Users of the platform can also decide to *downvote* a content, which decreases its value. In case of a downvote, no curation reward is awarded.

An important characteristic of Steemit is that bots are allowed in the system and their nature can be explicitly declared¹⁹. Note that the presence of explicit bots and of the rewarding system can have a high impact on the nature of a social network. The most common bots of the platform offer services which help users to gain visibility by upvoting or sharing their content to a large audience. These services usually require the payment of small sums of STEEMs or SBDs, fuelling the cryptocurrency circulation in the system.

Each account has a value associated, called *Reputation*, which measures the value of the contents users put on the platform. The reputation of the users does not affect any mechanism of the platform, but can be used to have an idea of how a user behaves in the platform. This is very important because, while STEEM, VEST, and SBD, which represent influence, dedication, and wealth on the platform, can be bought, reputation cannot.

¹⁷<https://steemd.com/witnesses>

¹⁸<https://steemit.com/witness-category/@someguy123/seriously-what-is-a-witness-why-should-i-care-how-do-i-become-one-answer>

¹⁹<https://www.steem.center/index.php?title=Bots>

B. Users' levels

A peculiarity of the Steemit community is that users are divided into levels based on their amount of VESTs. The users' levels along with the amount of VEST needed to reach each level is shown in Figure 3. It is important to notice that the amount of VEST needed to reach the next level is ten times bigger for each level. The inequality of this system is one of the criticisms made to Steemit. If an *orca* or a *whale* casts an upvote, it is very difficult for users belonging to lower levels to counter it with downvotes and this can be a problem if the creator of the content has bought the upvote, for instance from a bot. Furthermore, there is the problem of the large number of automated bots, which is a rather controversial topic, because some users use bots to increase their earnings, but others criticize them because they unfairly manipulate the value of contents, which instead should only depend on community members. Thanks to the sale of votes and to these voting bots, even low quality content can gain visibility and this contradicts the principles of the platform. Another decidedly criticized aspect is the phenomenon of *self-voting*; indeed, many users cast a vote to their own content at particularly propitious moment and, through this vote, they manage to obtain a much greater reward. Although this does not directly violate Steemit protocols, it is not a practice approved by many users, who believe that the contents value should not depend on the evaluation of the creator. All these aspects have partly contributed to a crisis of Steemit, which, starting from the second half of 2018, caused a decrease in the number of users, of other applications built on the Steem blockchain and of the value of Steemit cryptocurrencies.

The presence of self-voters, bots, and of the rewarding system represents the main motivation to study this system to understand how these aspects affect the characteristics of a Social Media.

IV. THE ANALYSIS OF STEEMIT FOLLOWER-FOLLOWING GRAPH

In this Section, we present the analysis of the Steemit Social Network model along with comparison with the one of other similar OSN services. Our analysis requires three main phases:

- Data collection. Collect information about the Steemit users by exploiting the Steem API;
- Graph construction. Build an appropriate representation of the Social Model (SM) of Steemit using graph theory;
- Graph evaluation. Evaluate the properties of the social graph built in the previous step.

In the following subsections we provide more details regarding each of the three steps.

A. Data collection

Steem provides an official API that enables the retrieval of a rich set of information about its users, such as, for each user, the date of the account creation, the set of his/her followers, the amount of STEEMs, VESTs, and SBDs owned, and so on. We collected the information of the accounts up to the 2nd of March 2019 using the official API²⁰.

The amount of accounts in the dataset is 1,223,473 and the distribution of the year of creation of the accounts is shown in Figure 4. As we can see, the platform gained its popularity in 2017, but the real peak occurred during the 2018 with more than half million of people joining the platform. The motivation behind the success lies in the latent global economic instability. The global economic crisis begun in 2007 provided fertile ground for alternative economies to sprout and develop. Especially in the field of cryptocurrencies, the widespread was due to two factors: the extreme ease with which everyone can have access to such market, and the high speculation expectation. The growth of popularity of Steemit was further motivated by the fact that users can easily and freely join the platform and have immediate access to all its functionalities, including the reward mechanism. The possibility for everyone to earn just by doing their normal activity on a social networking site was one of the early Steemit slogans.

We also acknowledge that there are many risks that can hinder the widespread of the BOSMs and Steemit in particular. This can be due to many factors, such as the fact that users do not see a concrete revenue right away by using the platform, as opposed to the aforementioned slogan of the platform. The motivations of this fact is that users need to wait for 7 days before unlocking the reward for a specific content they produce and that is the only reward they get for the content, i.e. any visibility the content will gain in the future will not grant additional reward. Moreover, the reward is granted as cryptocurrency in the platform, therefore additional steps are required to transform rewards into fiat currency, usable in the everyday life. However the cryptocurrency granted is also useful to be used in the platform in order to gain more influence, therefore users are not encouraged to sell it. Finally, the amount of rewards were probably not meeting the users expectations, leading to a progressive loss of activity. But there are also some external factors or events that affected cryptocurrencies at a greater extent. One such event is the so-called Great Crypto Crash²¹, which saw the majority of cryptocurrency lose up to the 80% of their value. New skepticism towards cryptocurrencies in general²² further contributed to the adjustment and reshaping of the phenomenon. It is, however, worth noticing that this did not lead to a death of the platforms. Instead, it led to a more comprehensive understanding of the effects of the coexistence of an economic layer alongside the social one. The biggest impact of this first revolution of BOSMs led other centralised platform to consider the possibility of including a cryptocurrency in their system. Up to date, the most important proposal was made by Facebook introducing Libra which, although not decentralised, will provide an economic layer to Facebook.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the year of the last vote cast by the users and of the year of the last post produced by them. The Figure confirms the increased popularity of the platform through the years, but also uncovers that most of the

²¹<https://business.financialpost.com/technology/blockchain/cryptos-80-plunge-is-now-worse-than-the-dot-com-crash>

²²<https://www.fnlonon.com/articles/nouriel-roubini-the-great-crypto-heist-20190719>

²⁰<https://github.com/steemit/steem-python>

Fig. 4: Distributions of account creation, last post and last votes.

TABLE II: Steemit followers-following graph properties

#Nodes	#Edges	density
1,223,473	98,092,374	6.6×10^{-5}
min degree	avg degree	Assortativity
0	80.17	-9.7×10^{-2}
max degree	max in-degree	max out-degree
844,863	102,021	828,403
#scc	size smallest scc	size largest scc
686,813	1	536,207 (43.8%)
#wcc	size smallest wcc	size largest wcc
69,939	1	1,153,521 (94.3%)

users actually never produced any content for the platform nor they cast a vote.

B. Graph construction

In Steemit, the social relationship that users can express is called "follow", which is asymmetric similarly to the one of Reddit and Twitter. In this paper, for consistency reasons, we decide to adopt a similar modelling of the social relationships used for Twitter [14].

We represent the Steemit relationships as a directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where V represents the set all users in the system, and E is the set of directed edges connecting a pair of nodes. An edge e from a node A to a node B, expressed as $A \rightarrow B$ means that A is a follower of B. In the rest of the paper we refer to this graph as the follower-following graph. In order to create the graph we parse the JSON file containing several financial and social information of the collected accounts. We extract the information related to the transactions used to express the social relations and enrich the information on the nodes with social and economic features, such as the number of contents created by the users and their balance in terms of cryptocurrency held.

C. Graph evaluation

Table II shows the properties of the Steemit follower-following graph. The number of nodes is 1,223,473, and the number of directed edges is 98,092,374, therefore we observe a very low density (6.6×10^{-5}). The degree of the nodes

Fig. 5: Indegree distribution.

Fig. 6: Outdegree distribution.

ranges from 0 to 844,463, but the maximum indegree is much smaller (102,021) than the maximum outdegree (828,403). There is an high discrepancy between the two values, however this effect can be explained by the unique social model of the platform. In fact, following other users is free, does not require a confirmation by the followed user, and can bring some visibility returns, up to the point where a single user follows more than 67% of the total users on the platform. On the other hand, attracting users on the platform is hard and requires a lot of effort, in fact the most "popular" user, in terms of plain number of followers, is followed by barely the 8.3% of the users.

To have a better insight of the degree of the nodes, we plot both the indegree and the outdegree distributions (Figures 5 and 6). The outdegree distribution fits a power law with $\alpha = 2.7$, which is typical of a random network, and does not show anomalies. The indegree distribution resembles a power law with $\alpha = 1.97$, that is just below the threshold 2, thus making it an ultra-small world. However it shows some anomalies as we see an unexpected number of accounts with almost 200 followers. This is possibly due to some gratification mechanisms of the platform (like achievements) or to the misconception that having at least a certain amount of followers is mandatory for earning money. Therefore people are attracted to easy methods to attract new followers, even if it is a paid service.

In order to investigate more in detail this detected anomaly, we decide to mix together the two distributions in the followers-to-following distribution (Figure 7(a)). As we can see from the Figure, most nodes have less than 1000 indegree and less than 1000 outdegree. It is interesting to notice that it is

(a) Followers-to-following distribution. On the x axis the outdegree and on the y axis the indegree. Each point in the plot represents a node with a specific indegree and outdegree, or, in other words, a user with a certain number of followers and following a certain number of accounts. The diagonal line is added to clearly show where the indegree is equal to the outdegree .

(b) An heatmap showing the density of the points in the Followers-to-following distribution, which describes how many nodes fall in the same order of magnitude by indegree and outdegree. This clarifies that most nodes have indegree between 1 and 9, and outdegree equals to 0, and that nodes are more likely to have a much higher indegree than outdegree.

Fig. 7: Followers-to-following distribution

very common for nodes to have an higher indegree rather than outdegree, as most of the points are over the black diagonal line. In order to highlight this characteristic, we show in Figure 7(b) the density of the points in the follower-to-following distribution, which describes how many nodes fall in the same order of magnitude by indegree and outdegree. This clarifies that most nodes have indegree between 1 and 9, and outdegree equals to 0, and that nodes are more likely to have a much higher indegree than outdegree.

In literature, it was shown that Twitter users that produce more contents tend to have a number of followers similar to the number of accounts they follow [31]. We performed a similar analysis, shown in Figure 8(a), where each point corresponds to a user, and the user is highlighted in fuchsia if it is one of the top 10% users by number of posts, green if it is one of the top 1% users by number of posts, and black otherwise. We discovered that in Steemit the users that produce more content are usually the ones with most followers. This is actually an effect of the rewarding mechanism: more followers grant users more visibility, which, in turn, grant more engagement to the content published, possibly generating even more followers. So users who are interested in generating a revenue from the platform have an interest in creating more contents to attract more users.

The degree assortativity coefficient, although negative, has a very small value, meaning that there is no assortativity nor disassortativity. The followers-following graph has several components, and it is worthwhile to notice that the number of Weakly Connected Components (WCC) is one order of magnitude smaller than the number of Strongly Connected Components (SCC). On the other hand, the size of the largest SCC is half of the size of the WCC, and it is composed by

almost 44% of the nodes.

To recap, the most important findings are the power law distributions of the degrees (Figures 5 and 6) and, that, if we consider the two distributions together (Figure 7) we observe that, although the maximum outdegree is higher than the maximum indegree, it is more common for nodes to have an higher indegree with respect to their outdegree. This shows how it is very easy to attract some followers, up to 1000, but it is extremely hard to attract more, while it is very easy to start following tens of thousands of accounts. This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that following another user is an easy task that can also be automatized by some users, thus creating a very long tail in the outdegree distribution, and unexpected anomalies in the indegree distribution. All together, these observations, suggest that the graph we are analyzing is a scale-free network, like other social networks.

D. The impact of rewards

We want to analyse the impact of the rewards and of the economic features on the social relationships created in the platform. In order to have a general view, we estimate if the stake in the platform is affecting the expected social behaviour. The economic stake of users in the platform can be measured by the economic resources invested. In Steemit, as we presented in Section III, there are three currencies: STEEM is the liquid currency, VEST shows commitment and power, and SBD is the stablecoin. Figures 8(b), 8(c), and 8(d) show the indegree and outdegree of the users, highlighting, in fuchsia the top 10%, and in green the top 1%, users with, respectively, most STEEMs, VESTs and SBDs.

For what concerns the top STEEM holders (Figure 8(b)), we can see that the vast majority of users follows a low number

(a) Followers-to-following distribution, but the top accounts concerning the number of contents created are highlighted. (b) Followers-to-following distribution, but the top accounts concerning the number of STEEM held are highlighted. (c) Followers-to-following distribution, but the top accounts concerning the number of VEST held are highlighted. (d) Followers-to-following distribution, but the top accounts concerning the number of SBD held are highlighted.

Fig. 8: Followers-to-Following Distribution

of accounts and up to few hundreds of followers. This is the typical behaviour of people that signed up just for investment purposes (buying STEEM and hoping that the price of STEEM goes up) and of the celebrities/public accounts. We also see another set of users who belong to the top STEEM holders who have hundreds of followers and are following up to one thousand other users.

In the case of VEST, yet again we see that the most of the users holding more VEST is following 0 or 1 other users and have few hundreds of followers (Figure 8(c)). This confirms that fact that "rich" people (on the platform) do not have a very active social life, but they rather accumulate value.

Lastly, users with most SBD have hundreds of followers and are following from tens up to one thousand of other users (see Figure 8(d)). Due to the different nature of the currency, this is preferred by users who are more active on the platform, especially considering that 2 months earlier SBDs were worth half the value²³.

Having noticed this discrepancy, we have inspected whether the social activity of the richest users is higher. To this aim, we compute the number of content produced by the users that are holding the most of each currency (Figure 9). We study only the number of content created because it is the main way to gain currency on the platform, besides buying it. In order to have a term of comparison with the general behaviour of the users, we also added the weighted average considering all the

users of the platform. The number of contents produced by the top STEEM and SBD holders is higher with respect to the one of the top VEST holders, which is counter-intuitive if we consider that content rewards are usually granted as VEST. However, the most important fact that we discover is that users belonging to the three categories have produced a very low amount of contents if we compare them to the platform average. This is a clear sign that the richest users are not the most social ones and that they got rich by buying stake, rather than earning it through the rewarding mechanism.

In order to further gain insight concerning the rewarding system, we propose an analysis of a selection of hotspot contents. Table III shows the 7 most upvoted contents in the platform, at the time of parsing, on the platform, alongside some information concerning the creators of the respective contents. There is a certain heterogeneity of the contents that appear to be the most upvoted. Indeed, by analysing the text, we find contents concerning Steem, Steemit, and blockchain in general, but also other topics, such as a makeup tutorial, two personal stories of users that got to know Steemit, and a photoshoot to advertise Steemit. The authors of the contents do not seem to be fishy or accounts spreading fake news, and most of them are either cryptocurrency enthusiasts or are personal accounts. The in-degree of the accounts is much higher than the out-degree, which means that they are able to attract a lot of interest. Considering the values shown in Table III, we see no correlation between the in-degree of the nodes with the number of upvotes, nor to the estimated rewards that these

²³<https://coinmarketcap.com/currencies/steem-dollars/>

Fig. 9: Number of contents created by the four categories. The first three categories are made of the 1% users that are holding the most STEEM, VEST, and SBD respectively. The last category is a weighted average of all users.

contents received. The fact that there is no clear correlation between the number of upvotes received by a content and the amount of estimated reward obtained by the creator of that content is a clear sign that the rewarding system is heavily dependant on the curators and their user levels. Indeed, as highlighted in Figure 3, the more VEST a user has, the more power it has in the platform, which translates, among other effects, in a bigger reward. But since some users grant their votes upon payment, the whole rewarding system can be easily fooled and low quality content creators can still receive high rewards if they buy votes from very influential users, while honest users are not able to counter this effect.

E. Steemit and other Social Media

BOSMs have been introduced as the next generation Social Media including all the social aspects of a common Social Network graph. For this reason, we decide to compare the Steemit follower-following graph with the analogous graph of others popular services. Table IV contains some important measures that help us understand at what extent Steemit is conditioned by the rewarding mechanism. In particular, we consider some Social Networks and Media services, where the data gathered ranges from 10^6 to more than 7×10^8 in terms of users, and from 5×10^6 to 7×10^{10} in terms of friend relationships. For clarity, we want to highlight that the different dimensions of the graphs do not affect the comparison provided in the rest of the Section, because the analysed network was proven to be a scale-free network in Section IV-C and therefore obeys to the laws that govern these networks [32].

The average degree of Steemit is 80, which is close to the one observed in the early years of Facebook [5], despite the fact that the dataset of Steemit is much smaller and the fact that on Facebook the number of social relationship is limited to 5000. Other datasets with sizes comparable to the ones of Steemit, for instance Flickr2007, LiveJournal2006 and Youtube2007 [6], show an average degree that is smaller.

Concerning the average shortest path between each pair of users, on LiveJournal is 5.99 and on Orkut is 4.21 [6]. On Facebook we have access to a more detailed analysis, as the average shortest path went down from 5.28 in 2008, to 5.06 in 2010, finally to 4.74 in 2012 [5], and it's not expected to go much lower, even if the nodes are connected in such a way to get the lowest average shortest path [33]. Finally, on Twitter one study claims that the average shortest path length is 4.05 on the directed follower/following graph [14], while another one claims it to be 4,12 in the directed follower/following graph and is 4.05 in the graph where only the reciprocated edges are considered [15]. The average shortest path on the symmetrized follower-following graph of Steemit is 3.7, which is a bit higher than expected, if the graph is an ultra-small world. In this case, probably the effect is caused by a relatively low number of nodes in the graph, within an ecosystem that is still undergoing a stabilization phase. Graphs with a similar number of nodes show a much higher average distance, while Weibo2016 [7] is two orders of magnitude bigger, but still showing a smaller average distance. The (edge) reciprocity of the edges is low if compared to the other directed graphs even though there is a strong bias depending on how the dataset is collected. The only dataset that is almost complete is LiveJournal2006 [6] for which the reciprocity is 73.5%, compared to 17% found in Steemit. Concerning the spid (variance over average) coefficient, we only have information about Twitter2009 [14] the Facebook snapshots [5], which dropped from 0.16 in 2008, to 0.1 in 2010 to 0.09 in 2012. The one in Steemit is 0.18 and it is similar to the one one registered in the early snapshots of Facebook. The assortativity coefficient in Steemit is close to 0, similarly to Youtube2007, but it was also computed on other platforms: 0.202 on Flickr, 0.179 on LiveJournal, 0.072 on Orkut [6].

Therefore, we can conclude that by the beginning of 2019 Steemit is undergoing a stabilization phase, but it is still showing some properties typical of an ultra-small world. The high values of average degree and average shortest path are similar to the ones showed by Facebook right after it opened to everyone, even though the number of users on Steemit is sensibly lower. We expect that it will become a much more clusterized community with respect to Facebook when the number of users will be comparable. We also think that these effects are largely caused by the economic rewarding mechanism, which is an incentive even stronger than plain sociality, to make bring people close.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper proposes an analysis of Steemit, a Blockchain-based Social Media in order to highlight its socio-economic aspects. We have chosen Steemit because it is one of the first example of BOSMs and in particular because it is the most popular BOSM platform used until now. The paper provided a detailed description of the system and of the three token defined in its economy. Furthermore, we presented an explanation of the rewarding mechanism and the factors that influence it. The main goal was the analysis of the follower-following graph and of other information related to

TABLE III: Properties of the top 7 contents per upvotes.

Account name	In-/Out-degree account	Account description	Content	Topic	Upvotes	Rewards
@xeroc	4,340/39	CEO of ChainSquad (blockchain company)	https://bit.ly/2CsJVjP	Piston (a Steem GUI)	1522	44,529.11\$
@infovore	7,861/132	Steemit enthusiast	https://bit.ly/32H96K4	Personal story	1436	17,349.65\$
@allasyummyfood	15,291/329	Food and travel	https://bit.ly/3eLJ6zy	Self introduction	978	17,093.16\$
@steemdrive	2,433/34	CEO of thecryptodrive (blockchain company)	https://bit.ly/2CFxzov	Advertisement of Steemit in South Africa	878	20,680.83\$
@cass	3,572/47	UI/UX designer	https://bit.ly/2ZNdx42	Rocketchat (alternative to Slack)	746	24,818.93\$
@guerrint	1,503/51	Makeup tutorials and Steemit enthusiast	https://bit.ly/3hr44FH	Makeup tutorial	656	26,660.04\$
@manthostsakirid	1,786/432	Photographer	https://bit.ly/2ZSJckR	Photoshoot	539	15,415.41\$

TABLE IV: Properties of social networks. For each dataset, we list the source and year, if the graph is directed, if it is a connected component, the number of nodes, the number of edges, the average degree, the average distance, the reciprocity, the spid, and the assortativity.

Source	←	CC	Nodes	Edges	AvgD	AvgDist	RE	spid	Assortativity
Steemit2019	yes	no	1.2×10^6	9.8×10^7	80.17	3.7	17%	0.18	-0.097
Weibo2016 [7]	yes	no	2.22×10^8	2.7×10^{10}	121	3.43	10%	-	-
Twitter2009 [14]	yes	no	4.17×10^7	1.47×10^9	41.7	4.12	36%	-	-
Twitter2012 [15]	yes	no	1.75×10^8	2×10^{10}	114.3	4.05	42%	0.108	-
Facebook2007 [5]	no	-	1.3×10^7	6.4×10^8	99.5	4.46	100%	0.15	-
Facebook2008 [5]	no	-	5.6×10^7	2.1×10^9	76.15	5.28	100%	0.16	-
Facebook2009 [5]	no	-	1.39×10^8	6.2×10^9	88.68	5.26	100%	0.13	-
Facebook2010 [5]	no	-	3.32×10^8	1.8×10^{10}	113	5.06	100%	0.1	-
Facebook2011 [5]	no	-	5.62×10^8	4.7×10^{10}	169.03	4.81	100%	0.09	-
Facebook2012 [5]	no	-	7.21×10^8	6.9×10^{10}	190.44	4.74	100%	0.09	-
Flickr2007 [6]	yes	W (26.9%)	1.84×10^6	2.26×10^7	12.24	5.67	62%	-	0.202
LiveJournal2006 [6]	yes	W (95.4%)	5.28×10^6	7.74×10^7	16.97	5.88	73.5%	-	0.179
Orkut2007 [6]	no	S (11.3%)	3.07×10^6	2.23×10^8	106.1	4.25	100%	-	0.072
Youtube2007 [6]	yes	W	1.15×10^6	4.94×10^6	4.29	5.1	79.1%	-	-0.033

user accounts, in order to understand the characteristics of the Social Media and how the reward can affect the social activity. The exploited information described the financial and social aspects of the users. Thanks to an all-round study of the follower-following graph we were able to prove that Steemit is an ultra-small world, although the rewarding mechanism influences the sociality of the platform, causing measures such as the average degree and the average distance to have anomalous values. Further analyses concerning the social activity of the users and their wealth on the platform proved that richest users are not the most socially active, which is caused by the possibility of users to buy cryptocurrency using external exchangers. From the user perspective, this has a big impact because owning wealth also corresponds to owning more power on the platform, especially in a social networking platform which aims to award users for their contributions. But this mechanism can be easily fooled by also letting users buy the same resources using external services which are willing to trade Steemit cryptocurrencies for other cryptocurrencies, such as Bitcoin. Moreover, we proposed a case study concerning hotspot contents which highlights a no clear correlation between the number of upvotes that contents receive with the rewards that these contents generated, fueling even more the criticism towards the possibility of buying upvotes from other users. Focusing more only on the social side of the platform, we compared the follower-following

graph of Steemit with the corresponding graph of other well known platforms already studied in literature. The analysis confirms that Steemit is a small world, but it is not as small as expected, showing properties similar to the early stages of Facebook.

As future works, we plan to analyse more in detail the anomalies we discovered until now, such as the weird shape of the indegree distribution, the motivations behind the differences between the degree distributions, and so on. Another interesting aspect that can be further evaluated is how the stake/wealth is distributed among the users, and why some users prefer to hold one currency over the others. Also, a temporal study of the evolution of the social graph would disclose more hidden properties, showing us which are the future possibilities of Steemit: will it succeed in becoming the platform for the next generation social media or not?

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